

1 **Evaluating heavy metal levels and their toxicity**
2 **risks in an urban lake in Chennai, India**

3 Daniel Rosado^{1,2,3*}, Franco Castillo¹, Indumathi Nambi², Rajagopal Sadhasivam²,
4 HimaBindu Valleru², Nicola Fohrer¹

5 ¹ Department of Hydrology and Water Resources Management, Institute for Natural Resource
6 Conservation, Kiel University, 24118 Kiel, Germany.

7 ² Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, 600036 Chennai, India.

8 ³ Indo-German Centre for Sustainability, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, 600036 Chennai,
9 India.

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11 HIGHLIGHTS:

- 12 • Pb, Cr and Cu in water of the Sembakkam lake pose a threat to biota
13 • Ni, Cr and Cu in sediment pose the highest risk for the biota of the lake
14 • Untreated wastewater is likely most relevant pollution sources

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17 CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

18 * Department of Hydrology and Water Resources Management, Institute for Natural Resource
19 Conservation, Kiel University, Olshausenstr. 75, D-24118 Kiel, Germany. Tel.: 0049 431 880 4889;
20 E-mail address: drosado@hydrology.uni-kiel.de (Daniel Rosado).

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1 Abstract

2 Many urban water bodies in Chennai, India receive untreated sewage that pollutes
3 their waters. An example is the Sembakkam lake, which waters reach the
4 Pallikaranai marshland, a proposed Ramsar site. In 2019, the city experienced the
5 worst water crisis in 30 years, and many lakes were extremely dry, favoring peaks
6 of heavy metals. Therefore, this study focuses on analysing heavy metal pollution
7 and evaluating its potential effects on biota.

8 In situ parameters were measured and water, sediment, and water hyacinth
9 samples were collected during four campaigns. Al, As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, and
10 Zn were measured in all samples. Digestions for total metal content were performed
11 in solid samples and acetic acid extractions only in sediments.

12 The average pH (7.89-8.46) was neutral-alkaline and electrical conductivities (1559-
13 2864 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) were high. In water, Pb (average: 2.59 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) posed the highest toxicity
14 risk according to the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, followed by
15 Cu and Cr. In sediment, Cu and Cr reached severe enrichment with respect to
16 continental crust (averages: 19.46 and 13.65) followed by Ni and Zn with moderately
17 severe enrichment. Ni produced the highest toxicity risk (average: 76.18 mg/kg),
18 above the effects range-median, followed by Cr and Cu, between the effects range-
19 low and effects range-median. The highest bioaccumulation factors in the water
20 hyacinth were in the roots. Translocation factors showed similar concentrations in
21 stems and leaves. Proper management of sewage is necessary to diminish the
22 potential deleterious effects of metals on aquatic life and by extension, human
23 health.

24 Keywords

25 Trace element; Lake ecosystem pollution; Heavy metals; BCR sequential extraction;
26 water hyacinth; South India
27

28 **1 Introduction**

29 The United Nations defined the sustainable development goal number 6 “ensuring
30 availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all” as one of
31 the 17 Sustainable Development Goals to be achieved by 2030 (United Nations
32 2015). It includes the target 6.6 “protect and restore water-related ecosystems,
33 including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes” (United Nations
34 2015). However, aquatic ecosystems are threatened by a variety of pressures such
35 as water abstraction, pollution, invasive species, pathogens, geomorphological
36 alterations, encroachment, and climate change, among others due to population
37 growth and industrialization (Pistocchi et al. 2017; Udias et al. 2020).

38 This is the situation of many urban water bodies in developing countries, including
39 in megacities, where larger numbers of humans are exposed to pollutants. A
40 common situation in these countries is that untreated sewage is discharged into
41 urban water bodies because of non-existing or non-properly-enforced regulations
42 (Fraga et al. 2020; Kumar et al. 2022; Das et al. 2022). In this context, heavy metal
43 concentrations can increase in water, sediments and living beings due to
44 bioconcentration and biomagnification and become a risk for human communities
45 nearby. In fact, some studies have alerted about this situation in many developing
46 countries, like Egypt (Abu El-Magd et al. 2021), Malaysia (Prasanna et al. 2012) and
47 China (Jiang et al. 2018). However, information on possible heavy metal related
48 risks for humans in the urban context is still scarce.

49 India has experienced a rapid increase in population, a significant economic growth
50 and an intense industrialization. After a protectionist period, the economy of India
51 was liberalized in the 1990’s and it became the world’s fastest growing major
52 economy between 2014 and 2018 (International Monetary Fund 2019). This
53 situation together with frequent discharges of untreated wastewater due to a lack of
54 sewage treatment and control over the industrial sector caused many aquatic
55 ecosystems to be polluted and their aquatic life to be reduced (Kelkar et al. 2011;
56 Chaturvedi 2012; Hossain et al. 2013; Sharma et al. 2018). As an example, the
57 sewage generation in the country was estimated to be around 62000 million liters
58 per day (MLD) in 2015 while the installed sewage treatment capacity was only
59 23277 MLD (Sharawat et al. 2019). Therefore, discharge of untreated sewage into
60 water bodies may be responsible for polluting three quarters of surface water
61 resources (Kumar and Tortajada 2020).

62 Chennai, the capital of the state of Tamil Nadu, has also experienced intense
63 population and industrial growth. Untreated domestic and industrial wastewater
64 discharges (Arappor Iyakkam 2017), garbage dumping, and others are threatening
65 the biodiversity of the city’s large number of water bodies (Lan et al. 2014). They

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66 include the Pallikaranai marshland, a proposed Ramsar site that was drained to
67 expand the urban area of the city and, consequently, reduced from around 50 km²
68 in 1980 to only 6 km² today (Vencatesan 2007; Steinbruch and Hörmann 2015; Sree
69 Sharmila and Swathika 2016). In addition, many artificial lakes, locally called tanks,
70 are located within Chennai. The tanks are traditional retention storages that
71 accumulated water during the monsoon season that was used for irrigation during
72 the dry season (Devi et al. 2020). The tanks were usually constructed by damming
73 intermittent streams using crescent-shaped earthen bunds in a cascade down the
74 axes of shallow inland valleys (Massuel et al. 2014; Devi et al. 2020). However,
75 water tanks became ornamental rather than functional when water provision shifted
76 to groundwater, resulting in their abandonment and degradation (Palanisami et al.
77 2008; Adelina 2015). It also affected the tanks in the Pallikaranai catchment,
78 including the Sembakkam lake, which waters reach the Pallikaranai Marshland. In
79 the Adyar catchment, siltation diminished water storage capacity of their tanks by
80 15% (Massuel et al. 2014).

81 Some studies have reported on the worrying levels of heavy metals (in this article,
82 the term heavy metal includes metals like Al, As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, and Zn,
83 measured in this work, and metalloids, i.e. As, etc.) in the water bodies of Chennai.
84 In Chemberambakkam lake, where water is collected for drinking water supply, Cd,
85 Pb, Fe, Co, and Ni in water were higher than the World Health Organization
86 thresholds for drinking water (Prabhu et al. 2015). Water in some lakes of south
87 Chennai has high concentrations of Cu and Pb (Lakshmi et al. 2018). In the Ennore
88 creek, abnormalities attributed to heavy metals were found on the Asian green
89 mussel *Perna viridis* (Vasanthi et al. 2017) and high concentrations of Fe, Mn, Zn,
90 Cu, Pb, and Cd were found in the flathead grey mullet fish *Mugil cephalus* (Arockia
91 Vasanthi et al. 2013). Jayaprakash et al. (2010) studied the sediments of the
92 Pallikaranai marshland and found they are more heavily contaminated with Cd, Hg,
93 Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn than in other regions on the southeast coast of India. In beach
94 sediments of Chennai, Pb and Ni were over the lowest effect level (LEL) and effects
95 range low (ERL) in several locations (Santhiya et al. 2011). The water hyacinth
96 *Pontederia crassipes* (formerly *Eichhornia crassipes*) is a plant that can concentrate
97 heavy metals in its tissues and it is even used in constructed wetlands (Newete et
98 al. 2016). Therefore, it can be used as an indicator or heavy metal pollution in waters
99 (Eid et al. 2020).

100 Heavy metals in water bodies can reach higher concentrations than usual during
101 drought events. Chennai suffers from drought regularly and it is ranked as the fourth
102 most vulnerable city to climate change in India (Kelkar et al. 2011). In the intense
103 drought event of 2019, many tanks were extremely dry and showed the lowest water
104 area of the period 2015-2020. The surface of the largest tanks shrank significantly

1 105 and some small tanks lost all their water (Jayaraman, 2019; "Water crisis in
2 106 Chennai", 2019).

3
4 107 Hence, this study aims to analyze the heavy metal pollution in water, sediments,
5 108 and water hyacinths of the Sembakkam lake and to evaluate their potential toxicity
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7 109 risks on the biota during 2019, including an extreme drought event. Therefore, this
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9 110 study is a valuable example for other urban lakes in Chennai and Asia that suffer
10
11 111 from similar pollution and climatic problems and contributes to a better
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13 112 understanding of the current water challenges in the region, and helps stakeholders
14
15 113 to implement management strategies to comply with the Sustainable Development
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17 114 Goals.

17 115 **2 Materials and methods**

18 19 20 116 **2.1 Study area**

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22 117 Chennai is the capital of the south Indian state of Tamil Nadu. According to the 2011
23
24 118 Indian census, the Chennai district had 7,088,000 inhabitants in an area of 426 km²
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26 119 and the agglomeration area had 8.70 million inhabitants in 1,189 km², i.e. the fourth
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28 120 biggest in India (Directorate of Census Operations Tamil Nadu 2011). The city is
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30 121 located on the southeastern coast of India (13°05'N and 80°18'E), on a flat area
31
32 122 known as the Eastern Coastal Plains with an average elevation of 6.7 m.a.s.l. and
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34 123 the highest point of 60 m.a.s.l. (Pulikesi et al. 2006).

35
36 124 The city has a tropical wet and dry climate (Köppen: Aw) with little changes in
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38 125 temperature throughout the year (Rajanikanth and Rajini Kanth 2020). Highest and
39
40 126 lowest average monthly temperatures in the period 1971-2000 ranged from 28.9 to
41
42 127 37.1°C and from 21.2 to 28.0°C (Selvaraj et al. 2016). The highest temperatures
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44 128 usually correspond to late May and early June and the lowest to January (Prakash
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46 129 and Punyaseshudu 2015). The influence of the northeast monsoon provides a high
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48 130 average annual precipitation of around 1,400 mm to Chennai, reaching 2570 mm in
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50 131 extreme years, like 2005 (Rajanikanth and Rajini Kanth 2020). Most of the rain takes
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52 132 place during the monsoon season, from mid–October to mid–December, and it is
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54 133 followed by a dry season (Selvaraj et al. 2016).

55
56 134 The two major rivers of the city are the Cooum River and the Adyar River. Both flow
57
58 135 from west to east and drain into the Bay of Bengal. The rivers are connected by the
59
60 136 Buckingham Canal, an artificial waterway that goes parallel to the coast (Mariappan
61
62 137 2014). The Pallikaranai catchment plays a relevant role because of its
63
64 138 environmental value and the pressures that it is suffering. This catchment contains
65
66 139 seven lakes, including the Pallikaranai marshland, a proposed Ramsar site
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68 140 (Shekhar 2020), and Sembakkam lake. The catchment was first comprised of vast
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70 141 agricultural lands and the Pallikaranai marshland before they were urbanized.

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142 Construction reduced the extension of the Pallikaranai marshland to only 6 km² from
143 around 50 km² in former times (Vencatesan 2007; Steinbruch and Hörmann 2015;
144 Sree Sharmila and Swathika 2016). In 2007, 3.17 km² of the wetland was declared
145 a Reserve Forest (Vencatesan 2007). However, there are two garbage-dump sites
146 on its outskirts and in 2006, a sewage treatment plant was built near the marshland.
147 Since then, the processed effluent is discharged into the water body (Steinbruch
148 and Hörmann 2015).

149 Traditionally, the Sembakkam lake (12.9321° N, 80.1543° E) and other tanks in the
150 catchment recharged its water during the monsoon season and provided water for
151 irrigation during the dry season. Due to urbanization, the lake became ornamental
152 and has suffered from degradation and abandonment. Currently, the lake is
153 recharged with untreated sewage throughout the year. Until 2018, there was a
154 landfill in the southwestern corner of the lake and still today, there are pumping
155 groundwater that is later sold as drinking water. The lakes suffer from heavy
156 pollution and eutrophication, making the water unsuitable for drinking, fishing, or
157 recreational purposes because of high levels of total dissolved solids, biological
158 oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, etc. (Raveen et al. 2008). Unfortunately,
159 compromised contaminated water is not only an issue in Sembakkam Lake, but also
160 in lakes such as Rajakilpakkam, Madipakkam, and Medavakkam (Raveen et al.
161 2008).

162 **2.2 In situ parameters, sampling and sample pre-treatment**

163 Twenty-two sampling points (Table S1) were selected throughout Sembakkam Lake
164 covering the whole lake area (Figure 1). Samples of water and water hyacinth were
165 collected in three sampling campaigns during the dry season (campaign 1,
166 04/07/2019; campaign 2, 07/08/2019; campaign 3, 04/09/2019). Sediments were
167 collected in campaigns 1 and 3 and in an extra fourth campaign (20/09/2019) during
168 the wet (monsoon) season, i.e. approximately every two months due to more stable
169 concentrations compared to water. Due to the severe drought of 2019 and the
170 subsequent reduction of the surface of the lake, some sampling points were
171 unavailable in campaign 1.

172

173 Figure 1. Sampling points in the Sembakkam lake, Chennai, India.

174 After collection, water, sediment, and water hyacinth samples were transported in
 175 less than 3 hours to the laboratories of the Civil Engineering Department of the India
 176 Institute of Technology Madras in a dark cooler (4°C).

177 Some water quality parameters were measured in situ (pH, electrical conductivity,
 178 and temperature) at each sampling point with a WTW 3630 IDS portable
 179 multiparameter meter (Xylem Analytics, Germany). Water samples were collected
 180 in 250 ml polyethylene bottles previously washed with 10% HNO₃ and Milli-Q water
 181 in the laboratory and rinsed three times with lake water afterwards. In the laboratory,
 182 water samples were filtered through 0.45 µm pore Teflon filters, acidified with HNO₃
 183 to pH 2 or lower, and stored at 4°C until analysis. These methods are in accordance
 184 with ISO standard 5667 parts 1, 3, and 4 and with common procedures in scientific
 185 publications (Villa-Achupallas et al. 2018; Gemeda et al. 2021).

186 Sediment samples were collected with a Van Veen grab at each sampling point.
 187 Only grabs that showed adequate penetration were retained. The sediment material
 188 collected with five full grabs was collected and later mixed and homogenized to
 189 obtain a representative sample from each point that was stored in a dark cooler at
 190 4°C. In the laboratory, the samples were dried at 60°C in an oven, disaggregated
 191 with an agate mortar, and sieved to fraction <63 µm (Jones and Turki 1997; Ouyang
 192 et al. 2002). Concentration of metals in sediments were referred to dry weight
 193 sediment (105°C). These methods are in accordance with ISO standard 5667 parts
 194 1, 12, and 15, and with common procedures in scientific publications (Rosado et al.

195 2015; Naifar et al. 2018).

196 Water hyacinth samples were collected in the Sembakkam lake manually from a
197 boat in the locations where it was present. Once in the laboratory, plant samples
198 were properly washed with Milli-Q water, and dried in an oven at 60°C until constant
199 weight. Dried samples were mechanically ground using a stainless-steel grinder
200 (particle diameter of 100 µm). The resulting powder form of the plant sample was
201 stored at room temperature until further analysis (Elmorsi et al. 2019).

202 **2.3 Sediment and water hyacinth digestions**

203 Sediment and water hyacinth samples underwent digestion in Teflon vessels in a
204 PicoTrace® digestion block with 5 ml Suprapur nitric acid (HNO₃) 65% (Merck,
205 Germany) and 0.2 g of sediment or water hyacinth at 140°C for 16 hours. After the
206 digestion phase, the block was cooled down to room temperature. The digestates
207 were filtered, made up to 50 ml with Milli-Q water, and stored in polypropylene bottle
208 in a fridge at 4°C before the metal analysis. For quality control purposes, all
209 digestion batches included a blank vessel with 5 ml of HNO₃ only and a reference
210 material vessel with reference soil SO-4 from the Canadian Certified Reference
211 Materials Project. Recoveries were greater than 90% with the reference material for
212 each metal and therefore considered satisfactory.

213 Sediments (1 g) underwent a extraction with 40 ml of 0.11 mol/L acetic acid prepared
214 from Suprapur acetic acid at room temperature as described in the first step of the
215 BCR-701 sequential extraction procedure (Pueyo et al. 2001) to obtain the acid
216 extractable fraction, the most labile fraction of metals in sediments. After the
217 extraction, the suspension was filtered and the filtrate was stored in a polypropylene
218 bottle in a fridge at 4°C prior to metal analysis. For quality control purposes, all
219 extraction batches included a blank vessel with 40 ml of acetic acid only and a
220 reference material vessel with reference material BCR-701 from the catalogue for
221 certified reference materials of the European Commission's Joint Research Centre
222 (JRC), achieving recoveries greater than 85% for all the elements and therefore
223 considered acceptable.

224 **2.4 Heavy metals measurements**

225 In water samples as well as digestates of sediment and water hyacinth samples, Al,
226 As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, and Zn were measured using an ICP-OES (Thermo
227 Scientific iCAP 6000) with axial and radial view.

228 **2.5 Data analysis**

229 The enrichment factor (EF) of heavy metals in sediments was calculated to assess
230 the magnitude of enrichment and the potential anthropogenic involvement (Buat-

231 Menard and Chesselet 1979; Aung et al. 2019). The following equation was
232 employed: $EF=(C_{\text{sample}}/Al_{\text{sample}})/(C_{\text{crust}}/Al_{\text{crust}})$, in which C_{sample} is the heavy metal
233 concentration in the sample; C_{crust} is the average heavy metal concentration in the
234 upper continental crust according to Wedepohl (1995) in mg/kg: Al, 77440; As, 2;
235 Cr, 35; Cu, 14.3; Fe, 30890; Mn, 728; Ni, 18.6; Pb, 17; Zn, 52; Al_{sample} is the Al
236 content in the sample; and Al_{crust} is the Al content in the continental crust (Wedepohl
237 1995). Aluminum was chosen as a normalization element due to its uniquely
238 lithospheric origin (Thiombane et al. 2019). The EF was interpreted as follows, no
239 enrichment (< 1), minor (1 – 3), moderate (3 – 5), moderately severe (5 – 10), severe
240 (10 – 25), very severe (25 – 50), and extremely severe (>50) (Amin et al. 2008;
241 Rastegari Mehr et al. 2021).

242 The bioaccumulation factor (BF) was employed to show how different water hyacinth
243 tissues bioaccumulate heavy metals. Thus, it was calculated as the ratio between
244 the element concentrations across three plant tissues (root, stem, leaves) and those
245 in its corresponding water: $BF=C_{\text{tissue}}/C_{\text{water}}$ (Carrillo-González and González-
246 Chávez 2006; Chamba et al. 2017). The translocation factor (TF) was utilized to
247 assess the transference of heavy metals from the roots to aerial parts (leaves and
248 stem) in the water hyacinth. Therefore, TF was calculated as the ratio between the
249 element concentrations in the aerial parts (stem, leaves) and those in the roots: TF
250 $= C_{\text{aerial}}/C_{\text{roots}}$ (Conesa et al. 2006; Chopin et al. 2008; Chamba et al. 2017). The BF
251 and TF are relevant factors when assessing the phytoremediation capacity of a
252 given species (Carrillo-González and González-Chávez 2006; Chopin et al. 2008).

253 R studio software version 1.4.1106 (R Development Core Team 2021) was used to
254 carry out analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's post hoc test to check
255 significant differences between temporal and spatial averages of heavy metals.
256 Also, a Pearson correlation test was performed to look for heavy metals with similar
257 behavior.

258 **3 Results and discussion**

259 **3.1 In situ parameters**

260 The average pH values recorded were 8.34 in campaign 1, 7.89 in campaign 2, and
261 8.46 in campaign 3. Hence, the pH was around neutral-alkaline. Although, the
262 interval between averages can be considered moderate (0.45 pH units), the ANOVA
263 test showed a statistically significant difference across sampling campaigns
264 ($p<0.05$). The Sembakkam lake receives a remarkable amount of sewage and
265 wastewater that can influence the pH of the lake as well as the higher influence of
266 rainwater throughout the year. These values fall within the range defined by the
267 United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) as suitable for aquatic life

268 in the National Recommended Aquatic Life Criteria Table (USEPA 2021a) and by
269 the Indian Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) for the propagation of wildlife and
270 fisheries (CPCB 1979; BIS 1992). Compared to other urban lakes in Chennai, the
271 Sembakkam lake shows values below the Velachery lake (8.87) but above
272 Perungudi (6.0), Karapakkam (6.1), Porur (6.2), Puzhal (7.0) and Nandhivaram
273 (7.02) (Raji and Abraham 2018).

274 The average EC values recorded were 2864 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in campaign 1, 1666 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in
275 campaign 2, and 1559 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in campaign 3. There is a decreasing trend in EC
276 values from campaigns 1 to 3, which could be explained by the increasing rainfall
277 recorded by the Chennai Metropolitan Water Supply and Sewerage Board
278 (CMWSSB) during the year (CMWSSB 2020). The ANOVA test confirmed a
279 statistically significant difference across sampling campaigns ($p < 0.05$). These
280 values are above the general range defined by the USEPA (50-1500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) for the
281 conductivity of rivers in the United States (Esfahani et al. 2015; USEPA 2021b) and
282 above the threshold value (1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) defined by CPCB for the propagation of
283 wildlife and fisheries (CPCB 1979; BIS 1992). The average of sampling campaign 1
284 is also above the threshold for potable water (2500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) of the potable water
285 directive of the European Union (European Council 1998).

286 Mean temperature values recorded for the water in the lake were 32.8°C in
287 campaign 1, 27.9°C in campaign 2, and 30.11°C in campaign 3. Temperatures also
288 showed a significant difference across sampling campaigns ($p < 0.05$) according to
289 the ANOVA test. Regarding dissolved oxygen, the values found were below 3 mg/L
290 during campaign 1 (mean: 1.86 mg/L). To support aquatic life, they are considered
291 “of concern” by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA 2021c)
292 and below the adequate levels to grow Salmonids and Cyprinids by the European
293 Union directive on the quality of fresh waters needing protection or improvement to
294 support fish life (European Council 2006).

295 **3.2 Water samples**

296 The ranges of heavy metal concentrations found in the water of Sembakkam lake
297 are presented in Table 1 and Figure 2. The overall mean concentrations of heavy
298 metals in water recorded in Sembakkam Lake were found to be Fe (11.89 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) >
299 Zn (5.55 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) > Ni (5.47 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) > Al (5.19 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) > Cu (2.84 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) > Mn (2.62 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) > Pb
300 (2.59 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) > As (0.88 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) > Cr (0.16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$). The average concentrations for every
301 campaign are shown in the supplementary material (Table S2). All the heavy metal
302 concentrations recorded in this study were relatively low compared to other polluted
303 lakes in India and around the world (Table 1).

304 Table 1. Heavy metal concentrations in water ($\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) in lakes in India and around the
305 world.

S. no	Study area	As	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn	References
1	Sembakkam Lake (India)	0.1 - 2.7	0 - 1.7	1.5 - 6.3	2.2 - 95	0 - 17.3	4.1 - 8.7	0.3 - 5.4	1.6 - 14.6	Present study
2	Hussainsagar Lake (India)	5.0 - 14.0	93 - 105	210 - 285	693 - 1173	208 - 428	81 - 459	78 - 261	236 - 409	Reddy et al. (2012)
3	Lake Beyşehir (Turkey)		27 - 28					65 - 96		Altındağ and Yiğit (2005)
4	Lake Victoria (Africa)		70 - 178					22 - 823	18 - 50	J. Mwita (2011)
5	Ichkeul Lake (Tunisia)			2.0 - 50	240 - 1950	30 - 250	20 - 200	10 - 500	40 - 450	Yazidi et al. (2017)
6	Taihu Lake (China)		0.07 - 2.84	0.11 - 1.06				0.26 - 6		Rajeshkumar et al. (2018)
7	Lake Burullus (Egypt)			20 - 420	1000 - 20900			2.0 - 18	24 - 38	El-Khayat et al. (2018)
8	Odra Lakes (Germany)		1.73 - 3.50	19 - 40	76 - 4291	25 - 2387	33 - 49	5.65 - 11.1	27 - 138	Ciazela et al. (2018)

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308 Figure 2. Heavy metal concentrations ($\mu\text{g/l}$) in the water of Sembakkam Lake,
309 Chennai, India.

310 Most of the metals studied were found harmless to the aquatic ecosystem when
311 compared with the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)
312 freshwater quality standards for the maintenance of aquatic life (Table 2). According
313 to these guidelines, all measurements of As, Ni, and Zn are classified as Class I,
314 indicating no anthropogenic pollution in the water (Figure 3). However, some
315 samples of Cr and most of the samples of Cu reach class II, which indicates that
316 concentrations are below the midpoint between natural and chronically toxic levels.

317 Finally, in the case of Pb, samples fell predominantly under class III and class IV,
 318 indicating concentrations above the midpoint between natural and chronically toxic
 319 levels and excursions beyond chronic criteria. Therefore, Pb represents the highest
 320 risk for the biota of the lake in terms of chronic toxic exposure. These concentrations
 321 are below the Indian thresholds for drinking water established by the Indian Bureau
 322 of Standards (BIS 2012).

323

324 Figure 3. Distribution (percentage) of the concentrations of heavy metals in the
 325 water of Sembakkam Lake, Chennai, India according to the classes defined in the
 326 UNECE guidelines for the maintenance of aquatic life (UNECE, 1994).

327 Pb causes deleterious effects on blood and kidney of animals as well as on their
 328 reproductive, nervous, and immune systems (WHO, 1989). Pb is known to
 329 bioaccumulate in organisms, mainly in biota consuming particulate matter, which is
 330 the case for benthic organisms. Hence they are the most likely to amass Pb to
 331 bioaccumulation up the food chain (WHO, 2019).

332 Table 2. Freshwater quality standards ($\mu\text{g/L}$) of the United Nations Economic
 333 Commission for Europe for the maintenance of aquatic life (UNECE, 1994). Class I:
 334 No anthropogenic pollution with inorganic matter; Class II: Concentrations are below
 335 the midpoint between natural and chronically toxic levels; Class III: Concentrations
 336 are above the midpoint between natural and chronically toxic levels; Class IV:
 337 Excursions beyond chronic criteria occur, but do not establish chronically toxic
 338 conditions in terms of concentration levels, duration or frequency; Class V:
 339 Excursions beyond chronic criteria concentrations allow acutely toxic conditions in

340 terms of concentration levels, duration or frequency.

Element	Class I	Class II	Class III	Class IV	Class V
As	<10	10 - 100	100 - 190	190 - 360	>360
Cd	<0.07	0.07 - 0.53	0.53 - 1.1	1.1 - 3.9	>3.9
Cr	<1	1.0 - 6	6.0 - 11	11.0 - 16	>16
Cu	<2	2.0 - 7	7.0 - 12	12.0 - 18	>18
Pb	<0.1	0.1 - 1.6	1.6 - 3.2	3.2 - 82	>82
Hg	<0.003	0.003 - 0.007	0.007 - 0.012	0.012 - 2.4	>2.4
Ni	<15	15 - 87	87 - 160	160 - 1400	>1400
Zn	<45	45 - 77	77 - 110	110 - 120	>120

341 Sembakkam Lake receives high input of untreated household effluents,
342 predominantly on the south side. It is located next to an unused landfill but decades
343 ago was surrounded by agricultural fields. Also, industrial effluents could be
344 discharged into the lake. Cu could be attributed to the high input of sewage from the
345 communities surrounding the lake (ATSDR, 2002). In regards to Pb, domestic
346 plumbing systems in which pipes, solder, and fittings contain Pb, including Polyvinyl
347 chloride (PVC), which can lead to high Pb concentrations in the water due to
348 leaching. Pb can also enter surface waters through the erosion of lead-containing
349 soil particles and the disposal of waste containing Pb products (WHO, 2019).

350 Heavy metal concentrations also exhibited significant spatial differences ($p < 0.05$)
351 between northern and southern areas of the lake in the case of Cu, Ni, and Pb. The
352 wastewater discharges could explain the higher concentrations located in the
353 southwestern part of the lake.

354 3.3 Sediment samples

355 3.3.1 Total metal content

356 The ranges of heavy metal concentrations found in the sediments of Sembakkam
357 lake are presented in Table 3. The overall mean concentrations of heavy metals
358 recorded in Sembakkam Lake were found to be Al (36945 mg/kg) > Fe (26124
359 mg/kg) > Mn (323.30 mg/kg) > Cr (212.59 mg/kg) > Zn (168.03 mg/kg) > Cu (134.42
360 mg/kg) > Ni (73.58 mg/kg) > Pb (14.42 mg/kg) > As (2.94 mg/kg). Averages of every
361 sampling campaign can be found in the supplementary material (Table S3). The
362 heavy metal concentrations recorded in this study were in the range of other polluted
363 lakes in India and around the world (Table 3). The concentrations for Al, Fe, and Mn
364 are compatible with other results reported in a study conducted by Tholkappian et
365 al. (2018) in Pulicat Lake, Chennai Coast of Tamil Nadu.

366 Table 3. Heavy metal concentrations in sediment (mg/kg) in lakes in India and
 367 around the world.

S. no	Study area	Al (mg/kg)	As (mg/kg)	Cr (mg/kg)	Cu (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	Mn (mg/kg)	Ni (mg/kg)	Pb (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)	References
1	Sembakkam Lake (India)	22575 - 46500	2.27 - 5.10	129.83 - 787.57	64.51 - 446.58	17213 - 40745	211.48 - 608.84	48.52 - 204.69	5.04 - 28.86	70.79 - 1008.74	Present study
3	Emerald Lake (India)			336 - 523	520 - 701	7 - 132900	0.314 - 0.462	151 - 158	20 - 53	128 - 215	Karthikeyan et al. (2020)
4	Ashtamudi Lake (India)			942.1	53.1	66387.9	1288.4	115	113.3	112.2	Hussain et al. (2020)
5	Baiyangdian Lake (China)		5.27 - 24.33	30.13 - 86	16.13 - 204.02			22 - 44	25.33 - 99.28	41.63 - 263	Ji et al. (2019)
6	Lake Tai (China)		11.37 - 37.86	49.22 - 210.37	21.27 - 149.94			26.32 - 123.41	21.85 - 49.31	79.31 - 417.96	Chen et al. (2019)
7	Demirköprü Dam Lake (Turkey)			6.75 ± 2.54	15.1 ± 4.6	15681 ± 7043		14.3 ± 8.1	6.5 ± 4.4		Öztürk et al. (2008)
8	Lake Victoria (Kenya)			3.81 - 6.61	18.88 - 61.42		826.6 - 3611.2	21.56 - 52.73	19.64 - 200.57	159.9 - 363.4	Ochieng et al. (2006)
9	Lake Texoma (USA)	9445 - 53285	6.0 - 16.0	12.0 - 51.0	9 - 136	7989 - 32046	145 - 643	6.0 - 31.0	5.0 - 15.0	33 - 242	An and Kampbell (2003)
10	Lake Geneva (Switzerland)			60.3 - 88.9	54.7 - 181.4				38.8 - 164.7	126.8 - 518.2	Haller et al. (2011)

368

369 Regarding EF values, the most enriched metals were Cu and Cr, showing mostly
 370 severe enrichment, as can be seen in Figure 4. Ni and Zn showed moderately
 371 severe enrichment. As, Fe, Mn, and Pb showed mostly minor enrichment. The high
 372 influx of untreated wastewater and leachates produced in the landfill nearby likely
 373 contributes to the enrichment, particularly in the case of Cu and Cr. Also, vestiges
 374 of pesticides containing Cu. Particularly for Cu, sewage sources can increase the
 375 Cu concentration in the sediment due to flocculation and binding to settling particles,
 376 or by complexation with natural ligands—e.g. humic substances (Leal et al. 1999).
 377 Other heavy metals, like As can also be enriched due to vestiges of pesticides
 378 containing As (Nikolaidis et al. 2004). In the case of Pb, in addition to the sources
 379 of domestic plumbing and others mentioned in the water section, the utilization of
 380 Pb in fuels in India until 2000 can explain a part of the enrichment of Pb in sediments.

381

382 Figure 4. Enrichment Factor (EF) for heavy metals in the sediments of the
 383 Sembakkam Lake, Chennai, India.

384 Long et al. (1995) provides adverse biological effects guideline values for heavy
 385 metals in sediments in the form of three ranges defined by the effects range-low
 386 (ERL) and effects range-median (ERM). The concentrations below the ERL value
 387 represent a minimal-effects range; a range aimed to estimate conditions in which
 388 effects would be rarely observed. Concentrations equal to and above the ERL, but
 389 below the ERM, represent a possible-effects range within which effects would
 390 occasionally occur. The concentrations equivalent to and above the ERM value
 391 represent a probable-effects range within which effects would frequently occur. The
 392 values of the ERL (lower) and ERM (higher) in mg/kg in dry weight of sediment are
 393 the following (Long et al. 1995): As (8.20; 70), Cr (81; 370), Cu (34; 270), Ni (20.9;
 394 51.6), Pb (46.7; 218) and Zn (150; 410).

395 When compared to adverse biological effects guideline values by Long et al. (1995),
 396 the concentrations for As, Pb and Zn were mostly below the ERL, which means that
 397 there is a probability of rare chronic toxic exposure to the biota of the lake. The
 398 concentrations for Cr and Cu were mostly in between the ERL and ERM values,
 399 meaning that there is a probability of occasional chronic toxic exposure to the biota
 400 of the lake. However, the concentrations recorded for Ni were mostly higher than
 401 the ERM values, meaning that Ni poses the highest risk for frequent chronic toxic
 402 exposure to the biota of the lake (Figure 5).

403

404 Figure 5. Distribution (percentage) of the concentrations of heavy metals in the
 405 sediments of Sembakkam Lake, Chennai, India according to the effects range low
 406 (ERL) and the effects range median (ERM) intervals defined by Long et al. (1995).

407 Correlated metals suggest a similar source of pollution (Zhang et al. 2018). The
 408 results of the Pearson's correlation matrix for concentrations in the Sembakkam lake
 409 sediment (Table 4) showed that across campaigns only Cu and Cr ($r=0.72$), As and
 410 Fe ($r=0.70$), and Ni and Cr ($r=0.94$) had an $r \geq 0.7$. These significant correlations
 411 suggest that they might be derived from untreated discharged sewage, leachates
 412 from the landfill, or other common sources.

413 Table 4. Pearson correlation matrix of metal variables in Sembakkam Lake across
 414 sampling campaigns.

	Al	As	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
Al	1	0.22	-0.08	0.26	0.51	0.26	-0.07	-0.28	-0.26
As		1	0.50	0.31	0.70	0.25	0.37	0.41	-0.10
Cr			1	0.72	0.40	0.16	0.94	0.61	-0.14
Cu				1	0.40	0.30	0.68	0.58	0.00
Fe					1	0.17	0.19	0.20	-0.24
Mn						1	0.13	-0.09	-0.07
Ni							1	0.58	-0.10
Pb								1	0.32
Zn									1

415

416 3.3.2 Acid extractable fraction

417 The average labile fraction of heavy metals followed a decreasing order of Mn
 418 (43.69%) > As (15.63%) > Zn (13.24%) > Pb (4.78%) > Ni (3.43%) > Cu (1.51%) >
 419 Cr (0.13%) > Al (0.05%) > Fe (0.04%) in Sembakkam Lake. A box-plot

420 representation can be found in Figure 6. Averages of every sampling campaign can
 421 be found in the supplementary material (Table S3). The results obtained in this study
 422 show similarities with those found by Chandra Sekhar et al. (2004) regarding the
 423 high labile fraction of Zn, and with Wang et al. (2016) and El Nemr (2003) concerning
 424 the highest labile fraction for Mn. Chandra Sekhar et al. (2004) reported that Zn, Cu,
 425 and Pb were the most labile metals in the sediments of Kolleu Lake, India. The
 426 averages of the labile metal concentrations were found to be as follows: Zn > Cu >
 427 Pb > Cr > Ni. Wang et al. (2016) reported that the average labile fraction of metals
 428 in the sediments of Lake Taihu, China, followed Mn > Zn > Cu > Ni > Pb > Fe. El
 429 Nemr (2003) studied surface sediments of Lake Urullus, Egypt, and reported the
 430 labile fraction of metals in the lake in decreasing order of Mn > Cu > Ni > Pb > Zn >
 431 Cr.

432
 433 Figure 6. Ratio labile/total metal concentrations in the sediments of the Sembakkam
 434 Lake, Chennai, India.

435 An ANOVA test was conducted between the north and south areas of the lake. It
 436 confirmed that there was no significant spatial difference ($p > 0.05$) for metals Al, As,
 437 Cr, Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb, and Zn. Only in the case of Mn, a significant difference was
 438 found.

439 3.4 Water Hyacinth samples

440 Regarding bioaccumulation factors, water hyacinth showed $BF > 1$ values for all
 441 heavy metals, which implies that the plant has an efficient bioaccumulation system
 442 in the roots and can be considered an accumulator instead of an excluder ($BF < 1$)
 443 (Yanqun et al. 2005). BF values are shown in Figure 7 and BF averages can be

444 found in the supplementary material (Table S4). The average concentrations of
445 heavy metals (mg/kg) in the tissues of the water hyacinth are also shown in the
446 supplementary material (Table S4).

447 The highest BF values recorded in this study were for Al followed by Fe, Mn, Cr, Cu,
448 Zn, Pb, Ni, and As (Figure 7). These results suggest that water hyacinth does not
449 absorb heavy metals homogeneously, and corroborate that absorption is not
450 concentration-dependent. The high BF values of Mn, Fe, Cu, and Zn correspond to
451 be essential plant macronutrients. Factors affecting heavy metal uptake and storage
452 by aquatic plants could be either biological, e.g. species, age, and physiology, or
453 non-biological (water physicochemical characteristics), e.g. temperature, salinity,
454 and pH (Bonanno and Lo Giudice 2010). Specifically, heavy metal uptake by plants
455 is influenced by heavy metal speciation such as humic complexes and free ions
456 (Bonanno and Lo Giudice 2010).

457

458 Figure 7. Bioaccumulation factor (BF) values in the leaves, stems and roots of the
459 water hyacinth *Pontederia crassipes* (formerly *Eichhornia crassipes*) across all
460 sampling campaigns in the Sembakkam Lake, Chennai, India.

461 The BF values of all metals were greater in the roots than in the aerial parts (stems
462 and leaves) and they differ significantly according to the ANOVA and Tukey post

1 463 hoc test results ($p < 0.05$). In the roots, the average BF of every metal can be grouped
2 464 according to the degree of accumulation in millions of times for Al (2,285,239),
3 465 hundreds of thousands of times for Fe (790,708), Mn (457,747) and Cr (353,451),
4 466 tens of thousands of times for Cu (19,281), Zn (17,030) and Pb (11,227), and
5 467 thousands of times for Ni (5,162), and As (2,311). This implies a limited internal
6 468 transport of heavy metals from the roots to the leaves and stem. Ephraim et al.
7 469 (2018) confirmed the bioaccumulation potential of the water hyacinth finding $BF > 1$
8 470 values and significant differences between the roots and the leaves for Ni, Cu, Pb
9 471 and Zn. The mentioned author found the highest BF for Ni and the lowest for Zn. In
10 472 a similar study, Eid et al. (2019) reported $BF > 1$ values and significant differences in
11 473 the roots compared to the leaves and stems for Mn, Fe, Cu, Zn, Cr, Pb, and Ni. The
12 474 authors found the highest BF for Mn and the lowest for Ni. Other studies also proved
13 475 the ability of water hyacinth to concentrate heavy metals in their roots (Kamari et al.
14 476 2017; Saha et al. 2017). The high capacity of the water hyacinth to store heavy
15 477 metals in their roots could be contributing to a depuration process in the lake and a
16 478 lower concentration of metals in the water.

17 479 Being an aquatic floating plant, water hyacinth absorbs heavy metals present in the
18 480 water through the roots (Téllez et al. 2008). Physiological barriers against metal
19 481 transport to the aerial parts are frequent in plants (Bose et al. 2008; Rahman et al.
20 482 2008; Saha et al. 2017). Metal binding proteins and the different biochemistry for
21 483 accumulation between the root and stem could explain the absence of translocation
22 484 to aerial parts (Lytle et al. 1998). Smaller and harder cations usually bind to the
23 485 smaller atoms like N and O in the roots, while when transferred to the leaves and
24 486 stems they bind to more complex composites such as oxalates and phytochelatin
25 487 (Lytle et al. 1998).

26 488 The differences between roots and aerial tissues can also be seen in the
27 489 translocation factor (TF) in Figure 8. In the present study, all of the heavy metals
28 490 recorded $TF < 1$ values, corroborating the water hyacinth's low translocation
29 491 capacity. Across all sampling campaigns, the highest average amount transferred
30 492 from the roots to the leaves came from Zn (0.49) followed by Cu (0.30), Cr (0.26),
31 493 Mn (0.14), Pb (0.12), As (0.11), Ni (0.11), Fe (0.04), and Al (0.04). The highest
32 494 average amount transferred from the roots to the stems came from Zn (0.27)
33 495 followed by Mn (0.25), Cu (0.24), Pb (0.12), Cr (0.11), As (0.11) Ni (0.11), Fe (0.04),
34 496 and Al (0.03). All the TF averages are depicted in the supplementary material (Table
35 497 S4).

36 498 In previous studies, Ephraim et al., (2018) recorded $TF < 1$ values for Cu, Ni, and Pb,
37 499 and only $TF > 1$ for Zn, Eid et al. (2019) reported $TF < 1$ values for Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni,
38 500 and Zn, and only a $TF > 1$ for Pb and Du et al. (2020) reported $TF < 1$ values for all
39 501 analyzed metals in their study: Cu, Pb, and Zn. These results coincide with the

502 present study regarding metals with $TF < 1$. However, they are in disagreement with
503 the metals with $TF > 1$.

504 Transport from the roots to the leaves and stem was mostly in a uniform manner.
505 Thus, most of the metals showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between Stem-
506 Leaves, with the exception of Mn, Zn, and Cr.

507

508 Figure 8. Translocation factor (TF) values in the leaves and stems of the water
509 hyacinth *Pontederia crassipes* (formerly *Eichhornia crassipes*) across all sampling
510 campaigns in the Sembakkam Lake, Chennai, India.

511 4 Conclusions

512 In this study, the heavy metal pollution in water, sediments, and water hyacinths of
513 the Sembakkam lake was evaluated. It was found that Pb and, to a lesser extent,
514 Cr and Cu in the water of the lake can pose a threat to biota due to toxicity. In
515 sediments, Ni poses the highest risk of frequent chronic toxic exposure to biota while
516 Cu and Cr pose a probability of occasional chronic toxic exposure. Also in
517 sediments, Cu and Cr showed severe enrichment, Ni and Zn moderately severe
518 enrichment and As, Fe, Mn, and Pb mostly minor enrichment. The severe and
519 moderately severe enrichments could be explained by anthropogenic sources of
520 pollution, like untreated wastewater as well as leachate produced in the closed
521 dumpsite in the southwestern corner of the lake. Water hyacinths are abundant and
522 their roots show concentrations up to hundreds of thousands of times higher than
523 the water, contributing to a depuration of heavy metals. However, stems and leaves
524 have concentrations significantly lower than the roots.

525 Proper management of sewage and waste is necessary to diminish the potential

1 526 deleterious effects of metals on aquatic life and by extension, human health. Further
2 527 research is needed to elucidate if the potential toxic effects identified in the
3 528 Sembakkam lake are similar in other lakes of the catchment and the Pallikaranai
4 529 catchment, and also in the fisheries and the surrounding groundwater that are
5 530 consumed by local communities.

9 531 **Statements & Declarations**

10 532 - **Competing Interests**

11 533 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose

12 534 **References**

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888 **Supplementary material**

889 Table S1. Coordinates of the sampling points.

Point	North	East
SM1	12°55'46.7"	80°09'16.4"
SM2	12°55'46.1"	80°09'20.1"
SM3	12°55'46.4"	80°09'12.4"
SM4	12°55'50.3"	80°09'10.1"
SM5	12°55'49.8"	80°09'15.3"
SM6	12°55'49.7"	80°09'21.4"
SM7	12°55'55.0"	80°09'22.6"
SM8	12°55'55.6"	80°09'17.9"
SM9	12°55'55.8"	80°09'12.8"
SM10	12°55'57.2"	80°09'07.5"
SM11	12°56'01.5"	80°09'09.4"
SM12	12°56'01.2"	80°09'13.9"
SM13	12°56'01.2"	80°09'17.8"
SM14	12°56'00.3"	80°09'21.6"
SM15	12°56'03.8"	80°09'21.4"
SM16	12°56'04.4"	80°09'18.0"
SM17	12°56'05.0"	80°09'14.3"
SM18	12°56'04.8"	80°09'11.0"
SM19	12°56'07.0"	80°09'15.3"
SM20	12°56'09.4"	80°09'16.3"
SM21	12°56'09.0"	80°09'18.5"
SM22	12°56'07.4"	80°09'21.0"

890

891 Table S2. In situ parameters and metal concentrations in the water of the
892 Sembakkam lake, Chennai, India.

		Sampling campaign			Average	
		1	2	3		
Water	In situ	pH	8.35	7.90	8.46	8.23
		Conductivity (µS/cm)	2864	1666	1559	2030
		Temp (°C)	32.80	27.99	30.11	30.30
Metals	Concentration (µg/l)	Al	11.53	3.27	4.52	6.44
		As	1.17	0.73	0.93	0.94
		Cr	0.24	0.12	0.19	0.18
		Cu	3.78	2.73	2.59	3.03
		Fe	26.31	9.18	8.72	14.74
		Mn	3.52	2.63	2.23	2.80
		Ni	5.42	5.29	5.69	5.47
		Pb	0.97	3.42	2.44	2.28
		Zn	4.34	8.00	3.61	5.32

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895 Table S3. Total fraction, enrichment factors, acid extractable fraction and ratio acid
 896 extractable fraction over total fraction in the sediments of the Sembakkam lake,
 897 Chennai, India following a digestion with commercial nitric acid (HNO₃) and 0.11 M
 898 acetic acid (AcOH) according to the BCR method (Pueyo et al. 2001).

Sediment	HNO ₃	Concentration (mg/l)	Sampling campaign			Average	
			1	3	4		
		Al	36743	37836	36835	37138	
		As	3.20	3.04	2.63	2.95	
		Cr	256.0	223.4	185.5	221.6	
		Cu	182.2	102.1	115.7	133.3	
		Fe	28472	25918	24855	26415	
		Mn	350.0	390.5	291.5	344.0	
		Ni	76.02	82.55	69.96	76.18	
		Pb	16.53	12.40	13.75	14.23	
		Zn	149.9	118.9	190.5	153.1	
		Enrichment factor	1	1	1	1	
		Al	1	1	1	1	
		As	3.43	3.12	2.84	3.13	
		Cr	15.22	13.30	12.42	13.65	
		Cu	25.78	14.72	17.90	19.46	
		Fe	1.97	1.72	1.73	1.81	
		Mn	1.02	1.09	0.87	1.00	
		Ni	8.42	9.25	8.73	8.80	
		Pb	2.07	1.52	1.88	1.82	
		Zn	6.10	4.71	8.74	6.52	
	AcOH	Concentration (mg/l)	Al	21.28	18.37	14.59	18.08
		As	0.45	0.35	0.46	0.42	
		Cr	0.37	0.18	0.26	0.27	
		Cu	3.42	1.45	1.68	2.18	
		Fe	29.73	9.58	5.03	14.78	
		Mn	140.1	152.3	136.2	142.9	
		Ni	2.19	2.13	2.50	2.27	
		Pb	0.52	0.59	0.66	0.59	
		Zn	15.79	12.17	33.94	20.63	
		Ratio AcOH/HNO ₃	Al	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05
		As	15.91	11.56	16.19	14.55	
		Cr	0.16	0.08	0.14	0.13	
		Cu	1.68	1.47	1.43	1.52	
		Fe	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.05	
		Mn	40.38	41.51	46.08	42.66	
		Ni	3.27	2.72	3.71	3.23	
		Pb	3.56	4.90	5.44	4.63	
		Zn	11.50	10.48	14.92	12.30	

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902 Table S4. Concentration, bioaccumulation factors and translocation factors in roots,
 903 stem and leaves of the water hyacinth of the Sembakkam lake, Chennai, India
 904 following a digestion with commercial nitric acid (HNO₃).

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Water Hyacinth	Concentration (mg/l)		Sampling campaign			Average				
			1	2	3					
Water Hyacinth		Leaves	Al	280.6	702.6	234.3	439.6			
			As	0.17	0.39	0.15	0.24			
			Cr	5.83	39.48	5.05	14.96			
			Cu	14.64	15.82	14.38	15.42			
			Fe	232	304	450	386			
			Mn	149.1	117.5	138.3	146.5			
			Ni	2.83	3.75	3.09	3.74			
			Pb	0.65	1.96	9.22	4.12			
			Zn	24.95	62.48	35.21	41.85			
			Stem	Al	315.7	340.0	203.8	375.4		
				As	0.24	0.21	0.20	0.26		
				Cr	6.58	9.17	3.34	10.79		
		Cu		7.09	32.19	4.85	16.19			
		Fe		218.5	398.9	277.8	420.3			
		Mn		244.4	248.7	271.1	265.1			
		Ni		2.08	5.21	2.19	4.78			
		Pb		0.40	3.58	8.19	4.14			
		Zn		15.01	27.69	22.71	25.29			
		Roots		Al	7770	13319	9328	8211		
				As	1.70	2.50	1.83	1.62		
				Cr	44.98	70.61	50.78	49.98		
			Cu	34.40	75.66	52.29	61.79			
			Fe	5648	10550	7885	6519			
			Mn	640	1136	1675	1060			
			Ni	22.69	34.18	28.25	25.41			
			Pb	6.52	25.52	48.69	60.04			
			Zn	57.72	95.37	92.67	89.26			
			Bioaccumulation Factor		Leaves	Al	26007	214694	51890	97530
						As	151	543	166	286
						Cr	27434	321653	27187	125425
		Cu				4229	5791	5561	5194	
		Fe				13096	33113	51611	32607	
		Mn				44508	44628	61989	50375	
		Ni				507	709	543	587	
		Pb				624	572	3774	1657	
		Zn				5837	7805	9755	7799	
Stem	Al	29266				103890	45135	59430		
	As	217				285	211	238		
	Cr	30962				74715	17976	41218		
	Cu	2049			11783	1875	5236			
	Fe	12326			43470	31871	29222			
	Mn	72963			94501	121491	96318			
	Ni	372			985	384	581			
	Pb	390			1046	3354	1597			
	Zn	3511			3459	6292	4421			
	Roots	Al			720298	4069577	2065840	2285239		
		As			1514	3436	1982	2311		
		Cr			211689	575316	273348	353451		
Cu		9936			27695	20212	19281			
Fe		318672			1149601	904450	790908			
Mn		191008			431722	750511	457747			
Ni		4061			6460	4966	5162			
Pb		6284			7455	19940	11227			
Zn		13502			11914	25675	17030			
Translocation factor					Leaves	Al	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.04
						As	0.10	0.16	0.09	0.11
						Cr	0.13	0.56	0.10	0.26
	Cu					0.43	0.21	0.28	0.30	
	Fe					0.04	0.03	0.06	0.04	
	Mn					0.23	0.10	0.08	0.14	
	Ni					0.13	0.11	0.11	0.11	
	Pb					0.10	0.08	0.19	0.12	
	Zn					0.43	0.65	0.38	0.49	
	Stem		Al	0.04		0.03	0.02	0.03		
			As	0.15		0.08	0.11	0.11		
			Cr	0.15		0.13	0.07	0.11		
			Cu	0.21	0.42	0.09	0.24			
			Fe	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04			
			Mn	0.38	0.22	0.16	0.25			
			Ni	0.09	0.15	0.08	0.11			
			Pb	0.06	0.14	0.16	0.12			
			Zn	0.26	0.29	0.25	0.27			

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